

Method for Determining the Resonant Frequency of Elastic Element of a Semiconductor Integral Converter. Patent SU, no. SU1516799A1

Abstract

The invention relates to vibration tests of semiconductor integrated converters. The aim of the invention is to improve the accuracy of determining the resonant frequency. During the tests, auto-oscillations of the elastic element of the converter are excited by the action of a smoothly varying pressure air stream on it. When the self-oscillation process is established, the resonant frequency of the transducer is determined from the change in the electrical output of its sensitive element. The specific property of self-oscillatory systems is in a stable mode of oscillation with a frequency equal to the natural frequency of this system, which leads to the achievement of the objective of the invention. 1 il.

1 Description

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(72) M.Yu. Tikhomirov, Yu.M. Spalek, V.V. Ponomarenko, and V.N. Borschev

(53) 620.178.5(088.8)

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Roylance L.M., Angell I.V.A. Batch-Fabricated filicon Accelerometer. -, Transactions on Electron Devices, 1979, Vol. ED-26, No. 12, p. 1911-1917.

(54) METHOD FOR DETERMINING THE RESONANT FREQUENCY OF ELASTIC ELEMENT OF A SEMICONDUCTOR INTEGRAL CONVERTER

(57) The invention relates to vibration tests for integrated integrated transducers. The aim of the invention is to improve the accuracy of determining the resonant frequency. During the tests, auto-oscillations of the elastic element of the converter are excited by the action of a smoothly varying pressure air stream on it. When the self-oscillation process is established, the resonant frequency of the transducer is determined from the change in the electrical output of its sensitive element. The specific property of self-oscillatory systems is in a stable oscillation mode with a frequency

equal to the natural frequency of this system, which leads to the achievement of the objective of the invention.

The invention relates to the field of vibration tests, and specifically to methods for determining the resonant frequency of the elastic elements of semiconductor integrated converters.

The purpose of the invention is to increase accuracy.

The drawing shows the test scheme for the proposed method.

When testing according to the proposed method, mechanical oscillations of the elastic element of the converter are excited, influenced by a smoothly varying pressure flow of air. Gradually increasing the pressure of the air flow, excite self-oscillations of the elastic element.

With a steady process of self-oscillations occurring at a frequency equal to the resonant frequency of the elastic element of the converter, this frequency is determined from the change in the electrical output signal of the sensing element.

Achieving the objectives of the invention is determined by the specific property of self-oscillatory systems - to be in steady-state self-oscillatory mode with a frequency equal to the natural frequency of the elastic element of this system.

Example. A batch of wafers 1 with silicon integral transducers designed to measure low-frequency vibration accelerations was tested. The elastic element 2 of the transducer is a monolithic structure in the form of a beam with a silicon inertial mass at the end. The inertial mass and the deformable region of the elastic element 2 are formed by chemical anisotropic etching on both sides of the KEF 1 silicon wafer with a thickness of 400 μm . Due to the etching of corners, using the square topology of the masking elements, after etching silicon to a depth of 370 microns, the inertial masses are made in the form of 12-sided truncated pyramids. Through $><$ -shaped notches 3 are formed by etching from the opposite side of the plate. The bridge measuring circuit of the converter consists of four connected by current-conducting tracks 4, diffusion tensor-resistive sensitive elements located in the deformable region of the elastic element 2 with a thickness of 30 μm .

According to the approximate calculation, the resonant frequencies in the manufacture of transducers are in the range (1.1 $\div$ 2.3) kHz. The plate 1 with silicon integral transducers was placed on a pad 5 specially designed for the probe device "Zond - A4M", which contained holes 6 to form an air flow through the $><$ -shaped notches and holes 7 to fix the plate on the pad using a vacuum. Then the air flow excites the oscillations of the elastic element 2. By placing the probes on the current-conducting tracks 4 and applying voltage to the measuring circuit, the value of the output frequency signal and the amplitude of oscillations of the elastic element at the minimum air flow rate are measured. Smoothly increasing the air flow rate through the $><$ -shaped notches 3, control the constant level of the output signal, the frequency and amplitude of the variable component of the output signal. In the steady-state process, when the frequency of oscillations does not depend on the increase of oscillation amplitude, the value of frequency, which is resonant for the elastic element of the given transducer, was fixed.

2 Claims

Invention Formula. Method for determining the resonant frequency of the elastic element of the semiconductor integrated converter, in which mechanical vibrations of the elastic element of the converter are excited and the resonant frequency is determined by changing the output electrical signal of the sensitive element, which differs in that, to improve accuracy, the excitation of mechanical vibrations is performed by acting on the elastic element of the converter by a smoothly changing air flow pressure, and the resonance frequency of the elastic element of the transducer is determined during the established process of its self-oscillation.

СОЮЗ СОВЕТСКИХ
СОЦИАЛИСТИЧЕСКИХ
РЕСПУБЛИК

SU 1516799 A1

СССР 4 С 01 В 13/00, С 01 М 7/00

ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЙ КОМИТЕТ
ПО ИЗОБРЕТЕНИЯМ И ОТКРЫТИЯМ
ПРИ ГКНТ СССР

ОПИСАНИЕ ИЗОБРЕТЕНИЯ
К АВТОРСКОМУ СВИДЕТЕЛЬСТВУ

ВВЕДЕНО В
ДЕЙСТВИЕ
Библиотека

1

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(54) СПОСОБ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ РЕЗОНАНСНОЙ
ЧАСТОТЫ УПРУГОГО ЭЛЕМЕНТА ПОЛУПРО-
ВОДНИКОВОГО ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ПРЕОБРА-
ЗОВАТЕЛЯ
(57) Изобретение относится к vibra-

2

ционным испытаниям полупроводнико-
вых интегральных преобразователей.
Целью изобретения является повыше-
ние точности определения резонансной
частоты. При испытаниях возбуждают
автоколебания упругого элемента пре-
образователя, воздействуя на него
плавно меняющимся по давлению пото-
ком воздуха. При установившемся про-
цессе автоколебаний определяют резо-
нансную частоту преобразователя по
изменению выходного электрического
сигнала его чувствительного элемен-
та. Специфическое свойство автоколе-
бательных систем находится в устой-
чивом режиме колебаний с частотой,
равной собственной частоте этой сис-
темы, обуславливая достижение цели
изобретения. 1 ил.

3 Similar Documents

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SU1275221A1	1986 – 12 – 07	Device for determining frequency response of ...
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SU1631252A1	1991 – 02 – 28	Measuring head
JPS63140939A	1988 – 06 – 13	Measuring instrument for surface characteristic
SU785740A1	1980 – 12 – 07	Apparatus for monitoring quality of ...
RU1796591C	1993 – 02 – 23	Device for checking piezoelectric pressure transducers
SUT408378A1	1988 – 07 – 07	Device for messuring acceleration

4 Priority And Related Applications

4.1 Priority Applications

Application	Priority date	Filing date	Title
SU874288015A	1987 – 07 – 21	1987 – 07 – 21	Method of determining

4.2 Applications Claiming Priority

Application	Filing date	Title
SU874288015A	1987 – 07 – 21	Method of determining resonatnt frequency ...